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The axiom of selection resolves Russell's paradox

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Abstract

We show that the axiom of selection solves Russell's paradox.

keywords: axiom of selection, Russell's paradox, axiom of foundation, axiom of antifoundation

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/pt8ax/download>
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Introduction

1. Russell's paradox is completely solved by Zermelo's axiom of selection [1].
2. These books help to understand this topic [2-4].

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Russell's Paradox

3. Most sets are not elements of themselves, that is, $\exists x \notin x$; one example is $x = \{1\}$, because $\{1\} \notin x$.
4. As we will see in (27), using the axiom of antifoundation, $\exists x \in x$.
5. Let $R = \{x : x \notin x\}$ be the set of all sets which are not elements of themselves.
6. If $R \in R$, then from $R = \{x : x \notin x\}$, we conclude that $R \notin R$.
7. If $R \notin R$, then from $R = \{x : x \notin x\}$, we conclude that $R \in R$.
8. (6) and (7) lead to $R \in R \leftrightarrow R \notin R$, which is a contradiction.
9. Therefore, $\nexists \{x : x \notin x\}$.

The axiom of selection

10. The idea is to modify the set $R = \{x : x \notin x\}$, assuming $x \in A$.
11. (10) solves Russell's paradox, as we will show in the following.
12. Let $S = \{x \in A : x \notin x\}$ be the set of all elements of A which are not elements of themselves.
13. If $S \in S$, then from $S = \{x \in A : x \notin x\}$, we conclude that $S \notin S$.
14. (13) is a contradiction, so $S \in S$ is impossible.
15. If $S \notin S$, then from $S = \{x \in A : x \notin x\}$, we have two possibilities: $S \notin A$ or $S \in S$. By (13), the second option leads to a contradiction. So, $S \notin A$.
16. The last case is: by (14), $S \notin S$. If $S \in A$, we must necessarily have $S \in S$, which is a contradiction.
17. In summary, we have the following three cases:
 - (a) $S \in S$ leads to a contradiction (13)-(14);
 - (b) $S \notin S \rightarrow S \notin A$ (15);
 - (c) $(S \notin S \wedge S \in A) \rightarrow S \in S$ leads to a contradiction (16).

18. So, $\exists\{x \in A : x \notin x\}$.

Note 1 (axiom of foundation)

19. **The Axiom of Foundation:** every nonempty set has an ϵ -least element [4],

$$\forall x(\exists z(z \in x) \rightarrow \exists z(z \in x \wedge \forall y(y \in z \rightarrow y \notin x))).$$

20. In other words, (19) leads to a finite ϵ -chain $x_1 \in x_2 \in \dots \in x_n$ for a finite positive integer $n > 1$ [4].

21. From (3), as a result of the axiom of foundation, $\nexists x \in x$.

22. From (21), $S = A$.

23. Therefore, $A = \{x \in A : x \notin x\}$.

Note 2 (axiom of antifoundation)

24. **The Axiom of Antifoundation:** there exists a unique set x such that $x = \{x\}$, where $x = \{\{\{\dots\{x\}\dots\}\}\}$ has infinitely many $\{\}$.

25. (24) is a result of $\aleph_0 = \aleph_0 + 1$, where \aleph_0 is the cardinality of the natural numbers.

26. (25) means that adding one element to the set of natural numbers do not alter its cardinality.

27. Within the axiom of antifoundation, $\exists x \in x$.

28. Considering (27), $S = \{x \in A : x \notin x\}$ assumes its most general form, and (22) is not necessarily true.

29. Let's call $x = \{\{\{\dots\{x\}\dots\}\}\}$ a *transfiniset*.

30. One interesting property of (29) is that $x = \{x\}$, and therefore $x = \{x, \{x\}\} = \{x, x\} = \{x\}$.

31. Generalizing (30), $x = \{x, \{x\}, \{\{x\}\}, \{\{\{x\}\}\}, \dots\}$.

32. Another property is $x = \{x\} = \{\{x\}\} = \{\{\{x\}\}\} = \dots$

Note 3 (empty set)

33. Suppose: $A' = \emptyset$, $S' = \{x \in A' : x \notin x\}$. The following are true:

(i) $\nexists x \in A'$;

(ii) $\forall x \in A', x \notin x$ (this is vacuously true);

(iii) $S' = \emptyset$.

34. Thus, if $A' = \emptyset$, then $S' = \emptyset$.

Final Remarks

35. The axiom of selection (12) resolves Russell's paradox ingeniously because it is used to create subsets of existing sets [1].

36. The axiom of selection cannot be used to create "excessively large" sets [1].

37. *Does Russell paradox hold within the axiom of antifoundation?*

38. *Is there a transfiniset $R' = \{x : x \in x\}$ of all transfinisets that are elements of themselves?*

39. *Is there a transfiniset $R'' = \{x : x \notin x\}$ of all transfinisets that are NOT elements of themselves?*

40. What are the properties of the *transfinisets*?

Open Invitation

Review, add content to, and co-author this white paper [5,6].

*Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Supplementary Files

[7,8]

How to Cite this White Paper

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Agreement

All authors are in agreement with the guidelines presented in [6].

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